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An Assessment Of The Causes And Effects Of Examination Malpractice Among Students In Umaru Musa Yar’adua University Katsina State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper undertook the study in order to ascertain and explored the causes and effect of examination malpractice among the students of Umaru Musa Yar’adua University Katsina State. In this paper empirical data were used from primary and secondary sources of data and analysis was made using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), The study adopted a survey descriptive research design a sampling was selected using Krejcie and Morgan chart to selected 302 students from the total population of 13,200 from the institution. 302 Questionnaires were given to the students but only 239 were returned. The study has four objectives, four research questions and formulated null and alternate hypotheses. The finding of the research revealed that, emphases on paper qualification contribute to examination malpractice among the students; examination malpractice leads to student’s expulsion from the university and poor learning condition also contribute to examination malpractice. It is concluded that fear of failure by the students is among the causes of examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar’adua university, Katsina. The research recommended that emphasis on paper qualification by the parent and government should be reduced in order to curb the menace among the students, learning environment should be well conducive with adequate learning facilities in order to encourage learning culture among the students and adequate supervisor/invigilators should be provided during the semester examination.

Keywords: Examination, Examination Malpractice, Students and Tertiary Institution.

INTRODUCTION

The issue of examination malpractice is one of the major factors that destroy the standard of education in our society. It is well known to us that; it is a criminal offence. In Nigeria, examination malpractice is one of the factors that raged our educational system thereby reducing the standard of teaching and learning in our institutions. This issue of examination malpractice has also generated more serious discussion among the Nigerian elites than any other educational issues recently. One of the issues that may compete with it along the same wave length is that of the cultism in our educational institutions. This is because, a part from its frequent occurrence at all levels of education, examination malpractice has eaten deep like canker worms into the fabric of the nation’s institutions. One of the objectives of education in Nigeria is to prepare the young ones to face future challenge and develop them to meet the nation’s manpower requirement. Schools need to conduct examination as a yardstick for assessment, It also a practical way of assessment in education.

Nigeria is known with emphases on certificates orientation which is gradually killing our educational sector. This certificate orientation has led to many people to acquire the certificate by all means either

by hook or crook. Therefore, all forms of misconducts and malpractice are still being introduced to achieve the eccentric menace. The development of our intellectual capacity is derailed to the fact that, stakeholders, government, administrators, teachers, lecturers, students and parents are primarily focusing on the end result of our education (certificate). Some people see the increasing rate of examination malpractice as a sign of the gradual decay of our educational system. In fact, the behavior of students towards examination and their eventual performances could be a rational base on which to assess the standard of education in any institutions. Salami (2002), said examination malpractice is an unlawful behavior or activity engaged by students to have personal advantage in an examination over their colleagues or mates who are competing in the same examination. Olujuwa (1999) simply defined examination malpractice as any examination not conducted in accordance with specific norms setup by the examination institution. Daramola (1992) said examination malpractice is an irregular behavior exhibited by candidates or anybody charged with the conduct of examination in or outside the examination hall, before, during or after such examination. Olayinka (1993) sees examination malpractice as a “misconduct of improper practice in any examination with a view to obtaining good results through fraudulent action”. Similarly, Rabi’u (2006), says examination malpractice involves various methods employed by candidate to cheat during examination. According to Onyechare (1996), sees examination malpractice as an illegality that is an unacceptable equally, an act or any act(s) of misconduct such as leakage, impersonation, writing on hidden part(s) of waves encoding/decoding or fingers for objectives tests, exchange of question papers and answer booklets committed before, during or after the examination by either students taking the examination or by officials assigned with the administration, evaluating or measuring the examination result is examination malpractice. According to Ene (1998), defined examination malpractice in psychological point of view, as form of cheating which directly or indirectly affect the ability of students’ performance. Therefore, examination malpractice is unacceptable conduct before, during or after the examination that warrant the application of appropriate sanctions against the alleged or guilty offenders.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the focus, concentration, attention and intervention strategies by the school’s management, Parents, Government, non-governmental organization, civil societies, and many other organizations or stakeholders to reduce the problem of examination malpractice among the students of higher institutions especially youth, the number of young adults are still increasing into examination malpractice. The issue of examination malpractice among the students in higher institutions provides negative impact on the higher learning institutions which causes high rate of corruption, low performance, and other educational disturbances in educational institutions due to examination malpractice.

Umaru Musa Yar’adua University Katsina State is not exempted from the issue of examination malpractice; some institutions in Katsina State are also among the institutions experiencing the declining of academic performance, apathy in learning activities. Therefore, this research will provide more information on the implications of examination Malpractice to the students to understand the causes and the way to curtail the engagement into examination malpractices, and helping them to know the importance of higher education to them and in the society. Many students are been withdrawn due to the issue of examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar’adua University, this motivated the researcher to undergo this important study in order provide knowledge on the implication of examination malpractice to the students of tertiary institutions.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this research is to provide an assessment of the causes of examination malpractice of students in tertiary institution in Nigeria and the necessary measure to be taken into consideration in reducing the examination malpractice among the students of higher institutions by enlighten them on the importance of higher education in the society, the research can also be used to improve and provide more information on the preventive measure on examination malpractice among the higher learning institutions students, most especially Umaru Musa Yar’adua University Katsina. This will help in choosing the most appropriate control mechanism and therefore reduce the level of examination malpractice.

Specific objectives include:

- i. To find out why examination malpractice occurs in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina State.
- ii. To find out the factors responsible for examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina State.
- iii. To ascertain the effects and the implication of examination malpractice among the students in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina State.
- iv. To provide some measures to be put in place in order to curb or provide a remedy for examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were set for the conduct of the research.

- i. Why examination malpractices occur in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina?
- ii. What are the factors responsible for examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina?
- iii. What are the effect and the implication of examination malpractice among the students in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina?
- iv. What is the measure to be put in place in order to curb or provide a remedy for examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina?

Hypothesis

H₁: Fear of failure by the student leads to Examination Malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

H₁: Emphasis on paper Qualification and Certificate leads to Examination Malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

H₁: Examination Malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina leads students to Expulsion.

H₁: Conducive Learning Environment with adequate Learning Facilities reduces the level of Examination Malpractices in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Literature Review

Passing examination has been erroneously conceived by many students as "life and death struggle", as passing examination to secure certificates is to many people the main goal of going to school rather than acquiring useful knowledge with which to cope with the demands of modern life. This attitude of an average Nigerian has made some people to doubt the validity and authentication of certificate issued to candidates at all levels of education. Examination malpractice has now become a vicious cycle and once students get involved and go through undetected, they easily become addicted and therefore fine-tune this "critical path" as a means of attaining academic success from the primary to the tertiary levels (Oluyeba, 1998). Examination malpractice is fast becoming an aspect of the student culture in higher educational institutions regardless of the school authority's preventive and punitive measures to discourage examination cheats. For instance, partial or total cancellation of results, suspension or expulsion of students from schools and the 21-years imprisonment stipulated by the Miscellaneous Offences Decree 20 of 1984, have not really deterred the culprits from the fraudulent practice (Oyekan, 1996). Also, according to the News Bulletin of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo (June, 2005), 30 students of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo who cheated in the Harmattan Semester Examinations of 2004/2005 academic year were subjected to a new disciplinary sanction of suspension from the college for either 4 or 5 academic sessions. But it is disheartening to note that this stringent measure did not deter some students as many other candidates were still caught cheating in the following Rain Semester Examinations of 2004/2005 session. This act does not only pose a veritable threat to the continued professional development of teachers but it is also capable of undermining the much needed morality vital to the overall productive education and progress of the society.

It is necessary at this juncture to undertake a theoretical discussion or definition of the concept of examination malpractice in order to place issues in proper perspective, Olumero (1992) defines examination malpractice as any examination not conducted in accordance with specified norms set up

by the Examining Institution, Oluyeba and Daramola (1992) view examination malpractice as any irregular behavior exhibited by candidates or anybody charged with the conduct of examination in or outside the examination hall before, during or after such an examination. Oyekan (1996) is of the view that delicate acts of indiscipline adopted by the students or their privilege accomplices to secure facile success and advantage before, during or after the administration of tests and examinations are referred to as examination malpractices. From the various definitions above, it is clear that examination malpractice involves all types of irregularities or illegal behaviors which characterized examination and compromises its ability or credibility as a valid test of student's competence and knowledge.

Definition of Concepts

Examination refers to the part of students' evaluation process that involves the determination of the intellectual ability, competence and the learners' level of understanding after a given training has been offered (Emaikwu, 2012). It is a means of evaluating the quality of knowledge, skills, capability, understanding that a person has acquired within a specified period of time (George & Ukpong, 2013). As a tool of evaluating academic performance, it is the basis on which the entire system of academics operates, rotates and it is an instrument used to decide whether a student will be allowed to move to the next level (Adegbenjo & Adebayo, 2017).

Examination malpractice is any action or deed that a candidate involves in, either during or after the examination, in collaboration with a staff in the academic system such as lecturers, invigilators, supervisors, examination officers or ones parents or guardians in a bid to obtain high grades (Onuka & Dorowoju, 2013). Examination malpractice is noted as fraud in the school system since the culprit ends up with undeserved grades. It also discourages the culture of hard work, decency, honesty, good behavior, determination and academic excellence (Amadi & Opuiyo, 2018).

Students refers to individuals registered and recognized as learners in educational institutions like colleges and universities for the purpose of acquiring knowledge and skills that could enhance personal developments to prepare them for the world of work. <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/students/47331>. For the purpose of this research, students refer to any individual attending schools whether primary, secondary or tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Tertiary Institution means any institution that provides post-school education on a full-time, part-time or distance basis. Tertiary also defined as university or other tertiary education provider recognized by the Employer which offers Degrees, Diplomas or teacher education courses.

Types of Examination Malpractice

There is belief and impression that examination malpractice is only linked to students. This is not so because the task and conduct of examination involves many people at various stages.

According to Ogunu (1991), Ivowi (1993), Denga (1998) and Ofono (2006) summarized and identified the following as the major forms of examination malpractice.

- i. Impersonation:** This is a situation where a candidate sits in an examination for another candidate, thereby pretending to be real or original candidate.
- ii. Insult or assault on examination officials:** There are cases students insulting examination officials as they carry-out their business. The aim is to distract them from effective supervision, so that they can have a way out.
- iii. Examination leakages:** this is a situation whereby some students lay their hands on the question papers before the commencement of the examination through the back door.
- iv. Collusion:** This is a situation whereby two or more candidates agree to receive or give assistance to each other.
- v. Assistance from Educational Stakeholders:** Examination stakeholders includes parent, teachers, lecturers, supervisors, security agents, printers, staff of examination malpractice body engage in one form of examination misconduct.
- vi. Electronically Assisted Malpractice:** in recent times, it has been discovered that, students make use of electronic gadgets/devices to cheat during examination.

vii. **Inscription:** Candidates have now advanced to the level of inscribing materials or information on anything like parts of their bodies for examples, baby pampers, dresses, handkerchiefs, rulers, chairs, tables, walls of examination halls and so on.

Coming to the examination halls with extraneous materials: This is a situation where students bring notes, textbooks, and so on into the examination halls.

Dimensions of Examination Malpractice

The following are some of the dimensions of examination malpractice as highlighted by Akinbi & Ayoola (2022).

i. Access to Examination Questions through Leakages

Leakages of examination question papers sometimes come through lecturers, faculty officers and examination officers. Students collect large amount of money and give to the above- named accomplices so that examination questions can be leaked (Sofola, 2004). Observations have indicated that when students have access to life questions, students tend to carry out their dubious acts by preparing the questions on answer scripts and smuggling them into examination rooms for submission. Some clever ones among them may take the life questions to friends or even teachers to discuss before the real examination.

ii. The Pairing Method

This method of cheating in examination is through collusion between two or more candidates who usually agree before hand to sit together and receive assistance from them. This formation of examination alliance is usually between the brilliant and dull students (Oyekan, 1996).

iii. Impersonation

This method of cheating is also very common in our Tertiary Institutions. It is a malpractice in which a student who writes gets paid or sometimes gets coerced to go and sit for the real candidate in order to pass the examination on behalf of the other candidate (Sofola, 2004). Some students have been found guilty of this act in Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye and have been expelled (OOU News, July 2006).

iv. The Giraffe Method

This method of cheating during examinations involves students stretching their necks unusually in order to have access to what others have written down with the intention of copying them (Ogunmola, 1998).

v. Copying from Handouts, Textbooks and Notes

Some fraudulent students often bring into the examination halls their notes, textbooks and handouts and copy directly from them. These materials may be hidden under their desks and are brought out for copying whenever the invigilator is out of sight.

METHODOLOGY

Description of the Study Area

Area of study refers to the geographical location to be covered by the study. In this case, the research will be conducted at Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina, the institution is located at Batagarawa Local Government Area of Katsina State; it is closer to Katsina Municipal which is about nine (9) kilometers to the city of Katsina.

Umaru Musa Yar'adua University was established under the Katsina State law promulgated in September 2006. The promulgation was informed by the desire to improve access to University education in view of the increasing number of qualified indigenous candidates. The University was conceived to serve as a nucleus for the socio-economic and political development of the State. It is expected to operate through both the conventional education system and distant learning modes in order to provide people of the State and the country with the necessary skills and technological orientation to serve as basis for self-reliance and good living. It was the hope and aspiration of the government of Katsina State, under the then leadership of late Alhaji Umaru Musa Yar'adua (Matawallen Katsina), and the people of the state to establish, nurture and develop a world class University. It is aimed to stand among other existing Universities in Nigeria and be driven by a modern information and communication technology (ICT) culture.

The University commenced its academic Programme in January, 2007. It began with twenty-six undergraduate courses at Faculty of Education, Natural and Applied Sciences and Humanities. By the 2012/2013 academic session, three (3) additional courses were introduced in the Faculty of Natural and Applied Sciences. In the same year, two additional faculties, Faculty of Law with one course, and Social and Management Sciences with five courses, were established, bringing the number of undergraduate courses to 35. Between 2012 and 2014, a Postgraduate School was established in three faculties, with 18 programmes. Also, to be established is the Faculty of Medicine, which will commence its programmes by the 2022/2023 academic session. The maiden convocation of the University took place on 16th February, 2013 with a total of 1,768 graduates for the 2009, 2010, 2011 and 2012 academic sessions.

Population of the Study

The population of this study was drawn from Umaru Musa Yar’adua University as higher institution located in the Katsina metropolitan of Katsina. The total population of the students was 13,200 students, academic office, (2024).

Method of Data Collection

Questionnaires are the main research mechanism for quantitative data collection. However, close ended questions was administered to the respondents on the scenario and modes of discussion to achieve the maximum experience of the respondents.

Method of Data Analysis

The study was employ descriptive analysis by use of means, percentage, and frequencies. Quantitative data was obtained from the close ended sections of the questionnaires and was analyzed using the thematic approach. The data was organized, tabulated, and analyzed in frequency tables, means, standard deviation, percentages with the help of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software.

Statistical Analysis

Data obtained were analysed using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency table, means percentage

RESULTS

The total population of the research was (13,200) which comprised the three tertiary institutions in Katsina state namely Umaru Musa Yar’adua University, Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic and Katsina State Institution of Technology and Management, Katsina. The sample size was drawn using the Morgan chart table was (302). Three hundred and two questionnaires were distributed to the respondents but only two hundred and thirty nine questionnaires were filled and returned.

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Tables 1. Gender of the Respondents

Option	Frequency	Percent
Male	183	76.6
Female	56	23.4
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 183 representing 76.6% were males while 56 representing 23.49% were females, this shows that males were more than the females as indicated by the table above.

Table 2. Age of the Respondents

Option	Frequency	Percent
Less Than 20 Y	18	7.5
20 - 30 YRS	183	76.6
31 - 35 YRS	15	6.3
36 - 40 YRS	18	7.5
50 and above	5	2.1
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 18 representing 7.5% were at the age of less than 20 years, 183 representing 76.6% were at the age of between 20-30 year, 15 representing 6.3% were at the age between 31-35 years, 18 representing 7.5% were at the age of between 36-40 years and 5 representing 2.1% were at the age of 50 and above years this shows that majority of the respondents were at the age of between 20-30 years as indicated by the table above.

Table 3. Marital Status of the Respondents

Option	Frequency	Percent
Single	177	74.1
Married	62	25.9
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 177 representing 47.1% were single, while 62 representing 25.9% were married this shows that most of the respondents which have the highest percentage out of the total sample size were single as indicated by the table above

Table 4. Level of the Respondents

Option	Frequency	Percent
100 Level	12	5.0
200 Level	22	9.2
300 Level	137	57.3
400 Level	43	18.0
Spillover I	12	5.0
Spillover II	13	5.4
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 12 representing 5.0% were at level 100, 22 representing 9.2% were at the level 200, 137 representing 57.3% were at level 300, 43 representing 18.0% were at level 400, 12 representing 5.0% were at spillover I while 13 representing 5.4% were at spillover II shows that majority of the respondents were at level 300 during this research work as indicated by the table above.

Table 5. Emphasis on Paper Qualification Promote Examination Malpractice

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	219	91.6
Not Agreed	20	8.4
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 219 respondents representing 91.6% agreed that emphasis on paper qualification promote examination malpractice while 20 representing 8.4% were disagreed, this shows that emphasis on paper qualification promote examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Table 6. Students unwilling to learn is among the Causes of Examination Malpractice

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	219	91.6
Not Agreed	20	8.4
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 219 respondents representing 47.1% agreed that Students unwilling to learn is among the Causes of Examination Malpractice while 20 representing 8.4% were disagreed, this shows that students boycotting to learn cause examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Table 7. Admitting more candidates above the Facilities responsible for Examination Malpractice

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	216	90.4
Not Agreed	23	9.6
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 216 respondents representing 90.4% agreed that Admitting more candidates above the Facilities responsible for examination malpractice while 23 representing 9.6% were disagreed, therefore, the research revealed that admitting too much students also lead to examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Table 8. Poor Learning Condition lead to Examination Malpractice

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	218	91.2
Not Agreed	21	8.8
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 218 respondents representing 91.2% agreed that Poor Learning Condition lead to Examination Malpractice for examination malpractice while 23 representing 9.6% were disagreed, therefore, the research revealed that Poor Learning Condition also lead to examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Table 9. Major contribution to Examination Malpractice

Option	Frequency	Percent
Fear of failure by the students	151	63.2
Desire of parents to see their children have certificates by all means	56	23.4
Inadequate Supervisor/Invigilators during examination	16	6.7
Graduating with Good Grades	16	6.7
Total	239	100.0

The above table indicated that 151 respondents representing 63.2% said fear of failure by the students cause examination malpractice, 56 representing 23.4% said desire of parents to see their children have certificate by all means cause malpractice, 16 representing 6.7% said inadequate supervisor/invigilators while 16 also representing 6.7% said graduating with good grades cause examination malpractice, therefore, the research revealed that fear of failure by the students cause examination malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Table 10. Examination Malpractice Breeds Corruption

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	196	82.0
Not Agreed	43	18.0
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 196 respondents representing 82.0% agreed that Examination Malpractice Breeds Corruption, while 43 representing 18.0% were disagreed therefore, the research indicated that Examination Malpractice Breeds Corruption in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina

Table 11. Examination affects students' morale and hard-work

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	225	94.1
Not Agreed	14	5.9
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 225 respondents representing 94.10% agreed that Examination affects students' morale and hard-work, while 14 representing 5.9% were disagreed therefore; the research

indicated that Examination affects students morale and hard-work in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Table 12. Adequate Learning Facilities and Good Condition reduce Examination Malpractice

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	220	92.1
Not Agreed	19	7.9
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 220 respondents representing 92.1% agreed that Adequate Learning Facilities and Good Condition reduce Examination Malpractice, while 14 representing 5.9% were disagreed therefore; the research clearly shown that Adequate Learning Facilities and Good Condition reduce Examination Malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Table 13. Reducing the emphasis on Paper Certificates reduce the level of Exam. Malp.

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	221	92.5
Not Agreed	18	7.5
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 221 respondents representing 92.5% agreed that reducing the emphasis on Paper Certificates reduce the level of Examination Malpractice, while 18 representing 7.5% were disagreed therefore; the research clearly shown that reducing the emphasis on Paper Certificates reduce the level of Examination Malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina as shown by the table above.

Table 14. Banning Electronic Gadgets reduce the level of Examination Malpractice

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	170	71.1
Not Agreed	69	28.9
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 170 respondents representing 71.1% agreed that Banning Electronic Gadgets reduce the level of Examination Malpractice, while 69 representing 28.9% were disagreed therefore; the research clearly shown that if management can do something by Banning Electronic Gadgets during examination can reduce the level of Examination Malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina as shown by the table above.

Table 15. Examination Malpractice leads to Students' Expulsion

Option	Frequency	Percent
Agreed	231	96.7
Not Agreed	8	3.3
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 231 respondents representing 96.7% agreed that Examination Malpractice lead to Students' Expulsion, while 8 representing 3.3% were disagreed therefore; the research clearly shown that majority of the respondents agreed that Examination Malpractice lead to Students' Expulsion in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina as shown by the table above.

Table 16. Most common nickname of Examination Malpractice

Option	Frequency	Percent
Expo	159	66.5
Missile	16	6.7
Exhibit	50	20.9
Weapon	9	3.8
Self-Defence	5	2.1
Total	239	100

The above table indicated that 159 of the respondents representing 66.5% stated that Expo is the most common nickname of examination malpractice, 16 representing 6.7% said Missile, 50 representing 20.9% said Exhibit, 9 representing 3.8% said Weapon and 5% representing 2.1% said Self-defence this shows that Expo is the most common nickname of Examination Malpractice in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina as indicated by the table above.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULT

Research the study revealed that, examination malpractice leads students to expulsion. The study also revealed that emphasis on paper qualification by the government, parents and the society is among the causes of examination malpractice as indicated from table 5 with 91.6%. Students unwilling to learn during and before the examination leads to examination malpractice with 91.6 percent. The study revealed that, admitting too many students above the available facilities cause examination malpractice among the students. Also poor learning environment can also lead students to examination malpractice as seen from table 7 with (90.4%). Fear of failure by the students was among the major causes of examination malpractice among the students with (63.2%) as indicated from table 9.

The research found that, examination malpractice also lead to corruption in tertiary institutions as indicated from table 10 with (82%). It was discovered that, adequate learning facilities and good learning environment reduce the level of examination malpractice among the students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina as indicated above. The research shows that reducing the emphasis on Paper Certificates by the government, parents and the general public reduce the level of Examination Malpractice among the students with (92.%) as indicated from table 13.

The research found that, banning Electronic Gadgets during examination reduce the level of Examination Malpractice among the students. Finally, the research revealed that, Expo was the most common nickname of examination malpractice

CONCLUSION

The effort of curbing the distorted and disturbing examination malpractice is responsibility of the government, parents, lecturers, school administrators, examination officers and examination bodies. Furthermore, in attempt to eradicate, fight or find solution to examination malpractice, all concerned individuals, stakeholders must rise up to see how to address the issue in the society.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Adequate learning facilities with good learning environment should be considered in promoting and encouraging students to learning culture.
- ii. The authorities in the higher institutions should try to organize a workshop or seminar related to effective handling of examination issues to the people responsible for handling examinations time to time e.g. Chief Examination Officers, College Examination officers, Examination Officers, Assistants Examination Officers.
- iii. School authorities should reward outstanding staff yearly especially those handling examination issues this will help more in keeping the examination secure.
- iv. The emphasis placed on certificate above other consideration should be addressed or minimized in order to reduce or eliminate examination malpractice among the students.
- v. Examination halls should not be too congestion to the extent of promoting copying from other students.
- vi. Materials and equipment needed for examination should be made available by the authorities in order to reduce administrative lapses.
- vii. Enough Supervisors and invigilators should be provided during the examination.
- viii. Wealthy parents should not support their children to pass examination by all means.

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